

Marine Robotics Workshop

Friday 25th October 2024, 11.30-13.00 (TBC)

hosted at the
Italian Conference on Robotics and Intelligent Machines
<https://i-rim.it/it/>
Rome, Gazometro Ostiense

Organizers

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Scope and format

Over 70% of our planet's surface is covered by water and over 96% of all Earth's water is in the oceans. The oceans host a wealth of natural resources and play a key role in environmental and climate change processes. Robotics may provide fundamental tools for studying, understanding, and exploiting the marine environment. Marine Robotics is characterized by specific challenges related to the adverse and harsh physical conditions (underwater pressure, waves, tides, currents, winds, salinity, biofouling, etc.) as well as technological issues (unavailability of electromagnetic transmissions underwater, low bandwidth acoustic communications, complex power management policies, etc.). This Workshop aims to cover the wide range of scientific, industrial and application interests regarding marine robotics. The language will be technical, but not academic to make the contents enjoyable by a not necessarily highly specialized audience. The speakers will illustrate recent trends and technologies and will provide a glance of possible future developments.

Program

Start	End	Friday 25 th October 2024 @ I-RIM 3D	
11:30	11:40	Welcome, David Scaradozzi, ISME - Univ. Pol. Marche	-
11:40	11:55	Speaker TBD	Italian Navy / PNS / CSSN
11:55	12:10	Speaker TBD	SAIPEM SpA
12:10	12:25	Speaker TBD	NATO STO CMRE
12:25	12:40	Speaker TBD	Leonardo SpA (TBC)
12:40	12:55	Speaker TBD	ISME
12:55	13:00	Final discussion/greetings	-